

Optimised for Whom? AI in Urban Energy, Transport, and Housing Between Efficiency and Structural Inequality

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1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence has become a central instrument for governing urban systems, enabling cities to manage energy consumption, traffic flows, and housing allocation. Yet the celebration of AI's problem-solving capacity coexists with a deeper paradox: the very systems designed to optimise urban life often reproduce the political and material inequalities they claim to mitigate. One example illustrates this contradiction: the proposed data centre in Caucaia, Brazil, sparked protests for imposing heavy environmental burdens on a water-stressed region, revealing how optimisation logics can override local ecological and social limits (Martins and Amorim, 2025). This controversy summarises a broader paradox: while AI is celebrated for optimising urban systems, its infrastructure reproduces environmental harm and reinforces existing inequalities.

This essay argues that AI primarily functions as a technology of optimisation incorporated within capitalist urban systems, generating efficiency gains while simultaneously projecting socially and environmentally unsustainable losses, thus reinforcing unequal power relations. Using insights from critical urban studies and technology governance literature, this analysis proceeds in three parts: outlining the theoretical basis of AI urbanism, examining its material contradictions, and assessing the conditions required for sustainable governance.

Within urban contexts, AI urbanism describes the growing influence of algorithmic systems on spatial planning, infrastructure, resource flows, and governance structures (Cugurullo et al., 2024). Central to this paradigm is optimisation, a logic that seeks to improve outcomes through data-driven prediction and control. Yet, aligning AI with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) remains complex: while AI can facilitate the achievement of 134 (79%) targets across several dimensions, it can also hinder 59 (35%) targets across social, economic, and environmental dimensions (Vinueza et al., 2020). These tensions underscore that optimisation is never neutral, but shaped by the political and economic structures in which AI is embedded.

2. Advances in Sustainability

37 Proponents of AI urbanism argue that algorithmic optimisation delivers measurable improvements in
38 resource efficiency, pollution reduction, and infrastructure management across energy, transport, and
39 housing sectors (OECD, 2019). This section examines three domains where AI evidently advances
40 sustainability metrics, while maintaining critical awareness that efficiency gains do not automatically
41 translate into equitable or ecologically sustainable outcomes.

42 **2.1 Energy: Smart Grids & Renewable Integration**

43 AI-driven smart grids revolutionise urban energy systems by dynamically balancing supply and demand,
44 integrating variable renewable sources, and reducing overall consumption. Machine Learning (ML)
45 algorithms predict consumption patterns and coordinate renewable energy sources through predictive
46 maintenance skills (UN-Habitat, 2022). AI models utilise various data types, including satellite images, to
47 create emissions predictions, providing essential insights for power system optimisation, infrastructure
48 planning, and disaster management (UN-Habitat, 2022, citing Mathe et al., 2019; Das et al., 2018). AI's
49 ability to balance supply and demand in real time is particularly valuable in smart cities, where energy
50 consumption fluctuates significantly with weather conditions, time of day, and population density (Singh
51 and Shah, 2024).

52 Barcelona, Spain, exemplifies smart grid implementation, applying AI-powered solutions in smart lighting
53 and waste management. The city excels in sustainability, reducing energy consumption, lowering carbon
54 footprints, and enhancing recycling rates (Singh and Shah, 2024).

55 **2.2 Transport: Route Optimisation & Emission Reduction**

56 Algorithmic transport optimisation targets congestion reduction, emission minimisation, and mobility
57 efficiency through interconnected systems aligned with SDGs 11.2 (safe transport access), 11.3
58 (participatory planning), and 11.6 (urban environmental impact) (UN-Habitat, 2022). AI systems manage
59 traffic flow by analysing real-time data from various sensors and cameras, allowing dynamic adjustments
60 to traffic signals and vehicle rerouting, significantly reducing congestion and improving urban mobility
61 (UN-Habitat 2022). AI is being used to learn about public transport usage through smart-card data and has
62 been employed to improve short-term estimation of public transit passenger volume (UN-Habitat, 2022,
63 citing Manley et al., 2018; Dai et al., 2018).

64 Moreover, multimodal integration represents a key advance in urban mobility systems. Bike-sharing and
65 electric scooter services offer alternatives for urban mobility that integrate well with public transportation,
66 with AI being used to integrate bike shares with other transport modes (UN-Habitat, 2022). Smart parking
67 systems through AI have been piloted, implementing sensors in parking spaces and communicating
68 information to road users through apps, with the potential to halve congestion in busy city areas (UN-
69 Habitat, 2022).

70 Singapore's city-state traffic management system, driven by AI and supported by real-time data inputs, has
71 substantially enhanced mobility through reduced congestion and travel times, while also anticipating and
72 mitigating potential traffic incidents (Singh and Shah, 2024). Likewise, Toronto, Canada, has applied AI to
73 optimise transit scheduling, leading to shorter wait times and more reliable public transport services (Singh
74 and Shah, 2024).

75 **2.3 Housing: Building Management & Resource Efficiency**

76 Smart building technologies apply AI to optimise multiple systems simultaneously, addressing SDGs 11,
77 9, 12, 7, and 3 (UN-Habitat, 2022). When smart devices powered by AI are included in building technical
78 systems during construction or renovation, users are better able to interact with these systems and adapt
79 them to their needs (UN-Habitat, 2022). Predictive maintenance allows cities to monitor infrastructure
80 conditions such as roads, bridges, and railways in real time, predicting potential failures before they occur
81 and scheduling repairs proactively, thereby reducing downtime, minimising disruptions, and extending
82 critical infrastructure lifespan (Singh and Shah, 2024).

83 By integrating AI with the Internet of Things (IoT), continuous monitoring and proactive maintenance of
84 critical infrastructure become possible (Singh and Shah, 2024). Real-time building data can be analysed by
85 AI to produce performance insights, allowing systems to anticipate required temperatures, adjust controls
86 accordingly, and identify faults (UN-Habitat, 2022). Mehdi's (2018) survey of intelligent buildings
87 documents 25–35% reductions in energy consumption through automated systems compared to
88 conventional management.

89 These applications demonstrate AI's technical capacity to optimise urban resource flows, achieving
90 measurable efficiency improvements across energy, transport, and housing domains. However, such
91 optimistic assessments legitimise critical interrogation: efficiency gains for whom? At what hidden costs?
92 Through what governance structures? The following section examines these essential questions, revealing
93 how optimisation generates profound material contradictions and structural inequalities.

94

95 **3. Material Contradictions & Structural Inequalities**

96 The physical infrastructure enabling AI-driven urbanism, such as data centres, computational facilities, and
97 digital networks, extracts massive quantities of water and energy from ecosystems already stressed by
98 climate change (Lee, 2025), disproportionately impacting vulnerable communities in both the Global North
99 and South contexts (Sharma et al., 2023). AI systems operationalise efficiency for capital accumulation
100 rather than ecological balance, integrating colonial patterns of resource extraction within allegedly “smart”
101 urban governance (Cugurullo, 2021). This section demonstrates how AI applications in energy, transport,
102 and housing reproduce and amplify existing inequalities through environmental externalisation, data
103 extractivism, and algorithmic discrimination (UN-Habitat, 2022), displacing costs onto marginalised
104 populations while concentrating benefits among high-income residents and technology corporations
105 (Sharma et al., 2023).

106 **3.1 Energy: Water Extraction & Computational Colonialism**

107 AI-driven energy optimisation masks significant material contradictions: computational infrastructure
108 consumes water resources at scales that threaten community access to necessities in water-stressed regions
109 (Barrat et al., 2025).

110 Data centres are often sited in arid regions to minimise corrosion, a practice that paradoxically concentrates
111 water consumption precisely where it is most scarce (Barrat et al., 2025). These systems require large

112 volumes of water to dissipate heat, intensifying resource pressures in already stressed regions. One study
113 projects that AI-driven facilities could consume up to 1.7 trillion gallons of water globally by 2027 (Fleury
114 and Jimenez, 2025). Recent investigations have identified 632 existing data centres, including 38 already
115 located in water-stressed areas and another 24 under development, collectively representing a 78% increase
116 in planned capacity (Barrat et al., 2025).

117 Evidence from multiple sites reveals systematic environmental degradation from data centres in
118 ecologically vulnerable regions. In Mansfield, Georgia, groundwater contamination has been documented
119 near Meta’s facilities, with water quality degradation in the same aquifer used by the data centre (Fleury
120 and Jimenez, 2025).

121 In Mesa, Arizona, a region experiencing extreme drought, authorities permitted Google’s data centre to
122 extract 5.5 million cubic meters of water annually, equivalent to 23,000 residents’ consumption. This
123 occurred while residential construction permits were revoked due to aquifer depletion, demonstrating
124 prioritisation of corporate infrastructure over community needs (Barrat et al., 2025).

125 Aragon presents an acute case study where 75% of the territory faces desertification. Amazon operates three
126 proposed data centres consuming 755,720 cubic meters of water annually, with applications pending for
127 substantial increases at existing sites (Barrat et al., 2025). Amazon has requested a 48% consumption
128 increase despite critical regional water scarcity. Environmental advocates argue this trajectory undermines
129 ecological resilience in an already stressed region (Barrat et al., 2025).

130 The proposed TikTok data centre in Caucaia, Brazil, exemplifies computational colonialism, resource
131 extraction from peripheral regions sustaining centralised digital infrastructure. The facility would consume
132 electricity equivalent to 2.2 million homes, exceeding 99.9% of Brazilian municipalities’ per-capita use. As
133 a single entity, it would rank as Brazil’s seventh-largest electricity consumer (Martins and Amorim, 2025).
134 This reflects asymmetric environmental burdens in the digital economy.

135 **3.2 Transport: Data Extraction & Municipal Sovereignty**

136 AI transport optimisation relies on asymmetric data exchange relationships, extracting valuable municipal
137 data while providing minimal reciprocal benefits, diminishing local governance capacity and concentrating
138 power within private technology corporations (UN-Habitat, 2022, citing Reuter, 2020; Aitken, 2017). Smart
139 mobility systems thus operate less as public-service tools than mechanisms for corporate surveillance and
140 capital accumulation (UN-Habitat, 2022).

141 This asymmetric exchange intensifies disparities by advancing neoliberal interests, technology-centric
142 governance, and data monetisation (Sharma et al., 2023). Technology corporations harness network effects
143 and data accumulation to create dependency relationships, positioning themselves as indispensable
144 intermediaries (Sharma et al., 2023). Extraction becomes continuous: every traffic sensor, signal-timing
145 adjustment, and congestion pattern feeds proprietary algorithms, while municipalities receive limited data,
146 insufficient technical capacity, and inadequate legal or financial means to develop independent analyses or
147 alternative policies, effectively ceding control to private entities whose obligations lie with shareholders
148 rather than public welfare (Hiroki, 2021; UN-Habitat, 2023).

149 This particularly impacts Global South cities, where limited budgets and expertise create greater
150 vulnerability to exploitative data exchange (Hiroki, 2021; Sharma et al., 2023). In Joinville (SC), Brazil,
151 for example, the Waze for Cities program created a dependency in which the platform retained software
152 and patents while providing only filters, partial information, insufficient for medium or large-scale traffic
153 planning (Hiroki, 2021). Although municipal officials recognised the imbalance, Waze’s market dominance
154 left few alternatives (Hiroki, 2021).

155 This dynamic reproduces colonial extraction patterns: data flows from periphery to core while analytical
156 capacity concentrates in Global North corporate headquarters (Sharma et al., 2023), weakening municipal
157 data sovereignty and limiting autonomous transport policymaking aligned with community needs rather
158 than corporate optimisation metrics (Hiroki, 2021).

159 **3.3 Housing: Algorithmic Discrimination & Access Barriers**

160 AI housing systems reproduce and amplify existing discrimination, creating algorithmic barriers restricting
161 access for marginalised communities while optimising real estate markets for investor profit rather than
162 residential need (Rosen and Garboden, 2024; Sharma et al., 2023). Smart building technologies and AI-
163 driven allocation mechanisms incorporate structural inequalities into automated decision-making (UN-
164 Habitat, 2023). Research on AI-driven rental platforms demonstrates that machine learning models trained
165 on historical housing data reproduce redlining patterns, systematically disadvantaging Black and Latino
166 applicants even when income and credit scores are controlled (Rosen and Garboden, 2024). These systems
167 operationalise discrimination through ostensibly neutral computation, prioritising investor returns and risk
168 minimisation over equitable access (Sharma et al., 2023).

169 Smart building technologies reinforce exclusion through cost structures that marginalise low-income
170 residents, while predictive algorithms identify gentrification opportunities for real estate investors,
171 accelerating displacement (Othengrafen et al., 2025, citing Naik et al., 2017; Reages et al., 2018). These
172 patterns reflect deeper contradictions in applying optimisation logic to social goods: algorithms trained to
173 maximise efficiency inevitably reproduce structural inequalities because historical data encodes centuries
174 of discriminatory practices (Sharma et al., 2023; Rosen and Garboden, 2024). Machine learning models
175 treat discrimination as a signal rather than bias, reinforcing racist market structures instead of challenging
176 them (Cugurullo and Xu, 2025). Algorithmic opacity obscures these dynamics, limiting accountability and
177 enabling corporations to maintain plausible deniability while restricting access for marginalised
178 communities (Cugurullo and Xu, 2025; Lee, 2025; Sharma et al., 2023).

179 Barcelona demonstrates how environmental improvements, when mediated by algorithmic housing
180 systems, can accelerate displacement. In Sant Martí, the creation of 18 parks between 1992 and 2006
181 attracted higher-income residents: the share of adults with university degrees rose by 27.92% and household
182 income increased by 26.7%, far above district-wide trends (Anguelovski et al., 2018). Market algorithms
183 classified the area as a high-return zone and labelled vulnerable residents as “high risk”, channelling
184 investment and driving up costs. As a result, low-income populations were displaced to Nou Barris, where,
185 despite the presence of green amenities, algorithmic systems continued to rate the neighbourhood
186 negatively, reinforcing structural inequalities (Anguelovski et al., 2018; Sharma et al., 2023; UN-Habitat,
187 2022).

188 These material contradictions reveal AI urbanism’s fundamental incompatibility with genuine sustainability
189 (Cugurullo, 2021; Sharma et al., 2023). Energy systems extract water from drought-stressed communities,
190 transport platforms extract data from municipalities, housing algorithms extract access from marginalised
191 residents, all while claiming optimisation and efficiency (UN-Habitat, 2022). The following section
192 examines how these structural inequalities demand alternative approaches centring justice, community
193 control, and ecological limits over technological optimisation.

194

195 **4. Conditions of Possibility**

196 Moving beyond simplistic views of AI as either a solution or a threat requires examining the material
197 conditions allowing other forms of AI-driven urbanism to emerge (Lee, 2024). Three transformations
198 emerge as essential: public data sovereignty (UN-Habitat, 2022), democratic participation in design
199 processes (Othengrafen et al., 2025) and optimisation metrics prioritising justice alongside efficiency
200 (Sharma et al., 2023).

201 **4.1 Public Data Sovereignty & Municipal Ownership**

202 Municipal and cooperative data ownership enables alternative outcomes prioritising equity alongside
203 efficiency. Barcelona’s Decidim platform demonstrates this availability, acting as a free and open data
204 commons digital infrastructure for participatory democracy (Bernardi, 2019). Decidim offers an alternative
205 to systems driven by profit and data extraction, designed to help citizens regain control over their personal
206 data and improve democratic processes (Bernardi, 2019). The platform shows that large-scale participatory
207 processes are possible, achieving a high implementation rate for citizen proposals (Bernardi, 2019).

208 However, Caucaia’s resistance against data centre infrastructure reveals that public ownership alone proves
209 insufficient without robust accountability mechanisms and capacity to contest corporate power (Martins
210 and Amorim, 2025). Data sovereignty must combine legal ownership with institutional capacity-building,
211 participatory governance frameworks, and community technical expertise enabling meaningful engagement
212 (Cugurullo and Xu, 2025; UN-Habitat, 2022).

213 **4.2 Participation**

214 Democratic participation in AI system design challenges technocratic decision-making that excludes
215 affected communities. Participatory design methodologies allow residents to define problems and evaluate
216 outcomes rather than accept predetermined optimisation metrics (UN-Habitat, 2022). The contrast between
217 Barcelona’s Decidim platform and exploitative arrangements like Joinville’s Waze implementation reveals
218 how governance structures shape technological outcomes (Bernardi, 2019; Hiroki, 2021).

219 Effective participation requires more than consultation; it demands redistributing decision-making power
220 over algorithmic systems, including community oversight of data practices, transparent audits, and
221 mechanisms to contest automated decisions (Sharma et al., 2023). The Aragon resistance against Amazon
222 data centres demonstrates how organised communities can oppose corporate infrastructure projects (Barrat
223 et al., 2025). However, participation power remains limited when state decisions override local
224 mobilisation, as evidenced by approval of contested permits during holiday periods (Barrat et al., 2025).

225 Genuine participatory governance requires legal frameworks protecting community veto power over
226 infrastructural developments, binding consultation requirements, and providing resources for communities
227 to develop the technical capacity necessary for meaningful engagement (Cugurullo, 2021).

228 **4.3 Alternative Metrics**

229 Reconceptualising optimisation metrics challenges the growth-oriented logic embedded in AI urbanism.
230 Doughnut Economics offers an alternative framework prioritising ecological sustainability and social
231 equity over GDP expansion, seeking human prosperity within social and planetary boundaries (Raworth,
232 2017; DEAL, 2024). Cities such as Brussels apply this model through DEAL’s ‘Data Portrait of Place’, a
233 tool for generating a holistic assessment of local social and ecological performance, identifying data gaps,
234 and setting new policy targets (DEAL, 2024).

235 The framework has expanded rapidly, and more than 70 cities worldwide are exploring adoption (DEAL,
236 2024). By establishing legitimate wellbeing metrics, the Doughnut model helps municipalities resist
237 corporate pressure for profit-maximising optimisation and challenge dominant growth paradigms (Raworth,
238 2017).

239 Yet implementation faces major barriers. The computational colonialism documented in Caucaia shows the
240 impacts of leaving profit-driven optimisation unchallenged (Intercept Brasil, 2025), while Barcelona’s
241 “green goods polarisation” demonstrates how environmental improvements can produce inequitable
242 outcomes when distributional concerns are sidelined (Anguelovski et al., 2018). These cases indicate that
243 alternative metrics must be paired with governance reforms ensuring algorithmic systems advance
244 collective welfare rather than capital accumulation (Sharma et al., 2023).

245 Together with public data sovereignty and democratic participation, alternative metrics form essential
246 conditions for sustainable AI urbanism. Nonetheless, their realisation is limited by corporate resistance,
247 institutional passivity, and structural power asymmetries favouring capital over communities (Sharma et
248 al., 2023; Martins and Amorim, 2025). Achieving genuine sustainability, therefore, requires moving beyond
249 tech-centric approaches, towards transforming ownership structures, governance models, and optimisation
250 logics themselves (Cugurullo, 2021; Sharma et al., 2023).

251

252 **5 Conclusion**

253 AI generates measurable gains in renewable integration (Vinuesa et al., 2020), mobility optimisation (Singh
254 and Shah, 2024), and building performance (UN-Habitat, 2022). Yet its infrastructures frequently
255 externalise socioecological harms, from water extraction in drought-stressed regions (Barrat et al., 2025) to
256 the erosion of municipal data sovereignty (Hiroki, 2021) and discriminatory housing outcomes
257 (Anguelovski et al., 2018; Rosen and Garboden, 2024). Its impact therefore turns not on technical capacity
258 but on governance structures shaped by corporate control and uneven resource flows, which reproduce
259 forms of computational colonialism (Cugurullo, 2021; Sharma et al., 2023). Achieving genuine
260 sustainability requires public ownership of data infrastructures, participatory institutions, and optimisation
261 metrics aligned with collective wellbeing rather than profit.

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